

Managing FAIR research products for biodiversity and ecosystems within the LifeWatch Italy Infrastructure

Andrea Tarallo¹[0000-0002-2749-8588], Cristina Di Muri¹[0000-0003-4072-0662], Martina Pulieri²[0009-0001-9691-1989], Francesco De Leo^{1,3}[0000-0001-9709-6114], Mariantonietta La Marra²[0009-0002-2070-7778], Davide Raho¹[0000-0001-6800-951X], Alberto Basset^{1,2,3,4}[0000-0002-3603-9316], and Ilaria Rosati^{1,3}[0000-0003-3422-7230]

¹ National Research Council (CNR), Institute of Research on Terrestrial Ecosystems (IRET), SP Lecce-Monteroni, 73100 Lecce, Italy

² Department of Biological and Environmental Sciences and Technologies, University of Salento, SP Lecce-Monteroni, 73100 Lecce, Italy

³ NBFC, National Biodiversity Future Center, Piazza Marina 61, 90133, Palermo, Italy

⁴ LifeWatch ERIC Service Centre, Lecce, 73100, Italy

Abstract. Biodiversity and ecosystem services are declining at an alarming rate, a trend expected to intensify due to human-induced climate change. Addressing this crisis requires comprehensive data collection and integration. However, the digital outputs resulting from the research lifecycle are often fragmented and heterogeneous. Combining these research products can yield new insights, but only if they are made Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, i.e. FAIR. Adherence to FAIR principles ensures that data and digital outputs can be integrated and reused by both humans and machines. In this context, national infrastructures are key in supporting the generation and management of FAIR digital outputs. This paper presents the LifeWatch Italy digital infrastructure, a national initiative developed to support the FAIR management of digital research products within the ecology domain. LifeWatch Italy aims to provide services and platforms that address key stages of the research data lifecycle, including data collection, curation, annotation, publication, and reuse. A suite of integrated platforms enables structured data ingestion, semantic annotation using controlled vocabularies and ontologies, taxonomic validation via national and international backbones, and publication in standardised, open formats. Interoperability is achieved through the adoption of widely accepted community standards, persistent identifiers, and automated workflows that ease the burden on individual researchers, ensuring that all the digital products meet FAIR principles by default. The infrastructure aspires to have a key role as national hub for biodiversity and ecosystem research in Italy, supporting the scientific community, and ensuring long-term usability of research outputs.

Keywords: National research infrastructure, Interoperability, FAIR Principles.

1 Introduction

Biodiversity and related ecosystem services are declining worldwide, with this trend expected to be exacerbated over the next decades by human-induced climate change acting under different scenarios [1]. Addressing the current and predicted biodiversity crisis requires intensive data collection to monitor changes in biodiversity across geographical and temporal scales and to develop effective knowledge-based conservation strategies [2]. Biodiversity monitoring and data collection are usually performed by different actors, including environmental agencies, research institutions, museums, NGOs, lay and specialised volunteers acting through a variety of monitoring programmes, often limited in their spatiotemporal and taxonomic coverage [3].

Thanks to a growing awareness of Open practices (Access, Science, Research, Source), the volume of available biodiversity data is growing at an unprecedented rate [4]. However, in many instances, they still lack fit for use, integration and reuse because of structural and technological challenges [5]. Although notable examples of global repositories for biodiversity data exist, such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) [6], most of the digital products of the research pipeline are often fragmented and dispersed across different sources, including scholarly literature, databases of public research institutes, government agencies, and generalist data archives [3, 7]. In addition, research products are highly diverse in nature, encompassing everything from raw and processed data to scripts and services, training materials, and they can be available in different structures and formats, limiting their interoperability across systems [8]. By combining different research products, e.g. datasets and analytical pipelines or web-services, scientists can aggregate and build on existing knowledge to generate novel findings or address different scientific challenges [9]. The use of standards and semantic artefacts provides an opportunity to overcome this challenge and integrate these digital products, yet their adoption is still inadequate, especially in some specific scientific domains [10]. To ensure the long-term value and reusability both by humans and machines, though, biodiversity data and related digital research products must adhere to the FAIR principles, which provide guidelines for their Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability [11].

In this context, national initiatives and infrastructures can play a crucial role in supporting scientific communities to generate FAIR digital research outputs that can be efficiently managed and integrated within different distributed information systems [5, 12-13]. Notwithstanding, when developing national infrastructural solutions for managing ecological information, all the challenges described above must be addressed. This paper introduces the LifeWatch Italy digital infrastructure, the result of a series of coordinated efforts to establish a national hub supporting the management of digital research products in ecology. LifeWatch Italy [14] is the Italian node of the LifeWatch European Research Infrastructure Consortium (LifeWatch ERIC) [15], the e-Science infrastructure dedicated to biodiversity and ecosystem research. In response to the growing variety and complexity of digital research products, LifeWatch Italy has significantly enhanced its infrastructure by envisioning a model that integrates services and platforms to support scientists throughout the entire research cycle, promoting best practices in data management and ensuring that research products are aligned with the

principles of FAIR and Open Science. In addition to bringing openness, reusability and long-term value to different research outputs, the LifeWatch Italy research lifecycle ensures interoperability between systems to overcome fragmentation and research silos. By facilitating data collection, curation, annotation, discovery, analysis and reuse through different interconnected components, this management model accelerates research progress and avoids time and effort consuming towards data wrangling for different purposes.

The following sections present the main components of the LifeWatch Italy infrastructure (see Fig. 1), illustrating how each platform and service supports the implementation of FAIR principles along the entire research lifecycle, from data collection to curation and validation, annotation, analysis and reuse. It should be noted, however, that individual platforms and services are not limited to a single purpose. They are designed to be flexible and to address multiple needs simultaneously, reflecting an integrated approach to research data management.

2 The research lifecycle in LifeWatch Italy

Fig. 1. LifeWatch Italy platforms and services to support the research lifecycle in the biodiversity and ecosystem domain. The figure shows the platforms developed for collection (green circles), curation and validation (dark orange circles), discovery (light orange circles), analysis (blue circle), and reuse (blue sky circle) of digital research products. Existing interconnections between platforms are represented with arrows. Dotted lines show future connections. Icons: Flaticon.com.

2.1 Collection

The LifeWatch infrastructure focuses on supporting the management and integration of research data. It usually does not directly engage in data collection activities such as field campaigns or monitoring schemes. Data collection is, however, increasingly becoming a multifaceted process, involving a wider range of contributors, including citizens and specialised volunteers, and leveraging emerging methods and technologies to support the on-site activities of these actors [16]. In response to this evolving landscape and accounting for the need to standardise these data and facilitate their ingestion into data management systems, two platforms have been developed: the Citizen Science Platform [17], designed to assist researchers in launching and managing citizen science projects; and the Bioacoustic Platform [18], aimed at collecting biodiversity data from recorded soundscapes. Both platforms are briefly introduced below.

Citizen Science Platform. Citizen science has emerged as an effective approach to involve the public in scientific research, particularly in biodiversity and ecosystem monitoring [19]. Citizen science activities often rely on user-friendly digital applications offering simplified data collection, facilitating participation and networking opportunities [16]. However, the maintenance, and management of digital applications for data collection present several challenges such as the need for specialised ICT skills for data management and safety storage, the infrastructural costs associated with large volumes of data, and the increasing demand for structured and rich metadata. In this context, the Citizen Science Platform has been developed to enable the creation of customisable web applications for data collection by the public. The platform supports various levels of user authorisation, allowing registered users to create and manage their own projects. Upon review and approval by the platform administrators, project leads can configure a dedicated project webpage for dissemination and customise a data collection web application. The web application allows for flexible configuration of observation parameters, including the collection of video and audio files, and automatically records the geolocation of each submission. The application is accessible via smartphones, facilitating widespread participation. Project administrators can access, validate, and analyse the submitted data, generating reports and enabling open access to validated records, which can be visualised on a map. The dataset can be downloaded into structured and interoperable formats to enable a facilitated ingestion by other LifeWatch services and platforms, e.g. the Data Portal. This solution offers a sustainable, cost-effective and scalable way for setting up and managing citizen science activities and their associated data.

The platform offers additional functionalities, including a) a section dedicated to fundamental knowledge about citizen science, including its history, methodologies, and key principles; b) a practical guide for developing and managing citizen science projects supporting users through the essential steps of project formulation, community engagement, data management, and communication; c) a searchable repository of training materials to support skills uptake in citizen science methodologies and

management; d) a comprehensive directory of citizen science projects, visualised on an interactive map.

Bioacoustic Platform. Non-destructive methods, such as camera traps, environmental DNA, bioacoustic monitoring, and remote sensing, in conjunction with technological advancements are considered game changers for biodiversity monitoring as they economise on human and natural capital [20]. Among these methods, acoustic monitoring has emerged as a particularly effective approach, especially when combined with artificial intelligence [21]. The integration of animal sounds with ecological information enables the extraction of valuable insights into ecosystems and species behaviour. The Bioacoustic Platform has been developed to support the recognition of species acoustic signals through the processing of spectral signatures. Registered users can upload audio recordings accompanied by relevant metadata. The platform analyses each recording and generates five visual representations of the sound: Time Fourier Transform, Spectrogram, Mel Spectrogram, Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients, and Waveform. A machine learning model trained to identify species provides a ranked list of probable matches by comparing the uploaded sound with existing recordings in the platform. Users can review these results and select the most appropriate match. This system facilitates the collection and management of audio recordings and associated metadata, such as geolocation. The platform provides a user-friendly solution for mapping species distributions, making it an optimal solution for initiatives that wish to engage both specialists and lay people.

2.2 Curation and validation

The scope of the curation and validation phase is to increase the quality of data by structuring and harmonising it to expected values and accepted semantic rules [22]. This phase encompasses syntactic validation, semantic annotation, and taxonomic alignment and, in the LifeWatch Italy infrastructure, it is enabled through the integration of multiple services and platforms. The LifeWatch approach maximises the reuse of existing technical solutions and standards, including (meta)data schema, semantic artefacts, and taxonomies, with the aim of aligning national efforts to community-accepted FAIR practices already in use within the community of ecologists.

Data Portal. Data curation and validation in the LifeWatch Italy infrastructure is mainly performed through a number of services embedded in the Data Portal [23]. The Data Portal serves as the primary access point to biodiversity data, including species lists and associated biological/ecological traits and/or co-occurring ecosystems and environmental data. In addition to data access, the platform has been developed and customised to support comprehensive data management, from curation and validation to publication and discovery of semantically annotated data and metadata. Accessibility is facilitated through the adoption of open formats, whereby the XML is used for metadata, following the Ecological Metadata Language (EML) 2.2.0 [24], and the CSV for datasets. The use of flat CSV files meets the needs of the scientific community, who

usually prefer to record their data in spreadsheets. Nonetheless, the Data Portal is designed to accommodate a wide range of data formats, including geospatial file formats. Data interoperability is supported by the utilisation of the Darwin Core (DwC) standard as data model [25]. The DwC is a widely recognised and adopted standard to share biological and ecological information. In addition to the DwC standard, other community-accepted controlled vocabularies and coding standards are used depending on the specific requirements and scopes of the datasets. Alignment with DwC and other discipline-specific standards supports data harvesting, aggregation and integration into other international biodiversity data initiatives. Prior to publication, datasets undergo a review and validation process via a structured data curation workflow, which includes the taxonomic validation of biological records and checks on the submitted metadata. Taxonomic data are cross-referenced and aligned against national and international taxonomic backbones, including the Italian backbone (see Italian Taxonomic Backbone section) and three Global Species Databases, i.e. the Catalogue of Life [26], the World Register of Marine Species [27], and the World Flora Online [28]. Submitted metadata records are subject to an automated validation of EML records using XSD (XML Schema Definition) that guarantees that metadata conforms to expected values, ensuring their syntactic accuracy.

Once approved by the portal's data managers, datasets and associated metadata are published, and a Persistent Identifier (PID) is assigned. By default, (meta)data records are granted with a Handle ID, while DOIs are provided upon request. Additionally, other PIDs are embedded into the metadata to ensure stable and persistent referencing among digital objects, supporting cross-system integration. These include ROR for institutional affiliations and ORCID for individuals. This approach improves traceability, citation, and discoverability of datasets and related resources, aligning with best practices in FAIR data publishing [5].

Semantic Annotation. Following the FAIR Principles, the primary objective of LifeWatch is to achieve standardised and interoperable data, both internally and across external infrastructures, within the domains of ecology, ecosystems, and biodiversity. Semantic artefacts play a pivotal role in enabling semantic interoperability, thus facilitating data integration and machine-readability [10]. To support this, dataset's metadata is semantically enriched using controlled vocabularies and ontologies. Users can annotate metadata using concepts/classes recalled via API from EcoPortal [29], the LifeWatch ERIC repository of semantic artefacts, or by using URIs from semantic artefacts available in other catalogues. By linking metadata attributes to concepts and relationships from ontologies or controlled vocabularies, it becomes easier to understand the content and context of data, enabling alignment across heterogeneous sources [30]. This approach helps overcome linguistic and structural ambiguities, ultimately fostering semantic interoperability.

Italian Taxonomic Backbone. Taxonomy is far from being a static science, it is rather a highly dynamic and investigative process [31]. As noted by [32], this dynamicity is captured within multiple independent initiatives, each with different aims and scopes

(e.g. taxon-specific or limited to specific areas) instead of converging over a single authoritative list of the world's taxa [33-34]. As a result, curated taxonomic information remains fragmented across numerous repositories [35].

With the rapid growth of biological data, accurately identifying taxa in datasets is a key requirement for ensuring data interoperability. In Italy, several research groups have been collecting taxonomic records of species occurring in the Country within different systems, from simple checklists to relational databases [36-38]. In this regard, LifeWatch Italy aim to provide a unified access point to all such taxonomic information and to align it with international standards, i.e. DwC.

- The Italian Taxonomic Backbone [39] currently includes:
- The complete Checklist of the Fauna of Italy, comprising approximately 27,000 animal species and subspecies provided by the Comitato Fauna d'Italia.
- The complete Checklist of the Flora of Italy, with nomenclature provided by the FlorItaly [37], which includes the most recent national checklists for native and alien vascular plants. Accepted names and synonyms comprise approximately 25,000 records.
- The complete Checklist of the Lichens of Italy, provided by ITALIC 8.0 [38] online database (<https://italic.units.it>), which includes around 17,000 records covering accepted names, basionyms, and synonyms for lichens.

The Italian Taxonomic Backbone is accessible through a web interface with the following features:

- Searching for one or more taxa;
- Viewing and downloading search results into CSV;
- Requesting modifications to existing taxa information or the addition of new ones. Each submission initiates a review process managed by an expert taxonomist for the interested group.
- Adding new checklists or updating existing ones, either manually or via API.

In addition, this service is recalled through API within the Data Portal and can be used for the taxonomic validation. The availability of these checklists, maintained and continuously updated by the national scientific community, along with the support of the LifeWatch Italy infrastructure facilitates the establishment of a robust and reliable centre for the aggregation and dissemination of biodiversity data in Italy, making it a key node for the sharing of accurate biodiversity information to international systems.

2.3 Discovery

Over the last decade, the field of e-Science has grown enormously to face the need of Big Data analysis and management. LifeWatch is deeply rooted in this context to develop an infrastructure that provides services to support the scientific community of ecologists in exploiting such data. However, "Small Data", i.e. data with few observations, in ecology are significant as they represent the greatest part of scientific activities, often focusing on manipulative or observational experiments on specific taxa or habitats [40]. Hence, data discovery and integration are key for such an ecosystem of "Small Data" allowing them to resemble Big Data especially when further manipulated and reused to address big scientific questions and challenges.

Semantic Platform. The use of ontologies for the integration of heterogeneous data sources is a common practice in information technology applications to achieve semantic interoperability within a data infrastructure, and across different infrastructures [41- 42]. LifeWatch Italy has developed an ontology-based approach for data discovery and integration by merging existing semantic artefacts, namely the SOSA Ontology [43], PROV Ontology [44] and DCAT vocabulary [45]. The resulting model was extended to include taxonomic and ecological concepts. Data and metadata are then mapped against the ontology to produce RDF triples organised into knowledge graphs, networks of entities and relationships among them. Knowledge graphs are accessible and searchable through the web interface of the Semantic Platform [46], which offers a powerful and intuitive way to explore and interact with a wide range of interconnected data. The platform provides extensive search capabilities across multiple variables, people and organisations, geo-temporal contexts, taxonomies and measurements. Users can integrate heterogeneous data sources through semantically enriched queries (SPARQL), generating custom datasets that can be exported and reused within external systems and services.

Metadata Catalogue. All the research products can be discovered within the LifeWatch Italy Metadata Catalogue [47], a unique access point to data, workflows, Virtual Research Environments (VREs), services, scripts, and training resources. Metadata can be searched through a web interface with simple and advanced searching options, allowing users to refine criteria using facets and search boxes. Records are available through structured and descriptive metadata based on international standards, Ecological Metadata Language (EML 2.2.0) and ISO 19139, thus promoting metadata sharing and exchange across organisations and infrastructures [30]. In addition to these standards, users can request additional metadata schemas or profiles to the platform's admins providing a certain level of flexibility based on users' needs.

The catalogue includes the F-UJI tool [48], a service to evaluate the FAIRness of metadata using the assessment metrics defined by the FAIRsFAIR project [49]. The service performs evaluations on individual metadata records and the catalogue as a whole, delivering detailed reports with scores for each FAIR metric. Prior publication, users can check the FAIR assessment report, enabling them to enhance the FAIR score by supplying additional metadata descriptions. Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) can be assigned upon request to ensure the persistent identification and citation of metadata records.

2.4 Analysis

DataLabs. Computational analysis is crucial to discover meaningful patterns, especially in the current era characterised by high volume, velocity and variety of data [50]. In this context, analytical scripts and services should have immediate access to the most up-to-date data and metadata and they should as well be described through structured metadata and with compatible encodings based on community-accepted standards [51]. In essence, cloud computation and connections between (meta)data

management systems and computational systems are pivotal to ensure reliable, repeatable and reproducible analyses. To this aim, LifeWatch Italy has developed DataLabs [52], a coding platform designed to support collaborative and documented data analysis within a multi-user environment. Powered by JupyterHub, it enables the scalable and secure deployment of personalized JupyterLab instances [53], facilitating access to reproducible workflows across research teams.

The platform integrates three different programming languages, commonly used in the field of environmental science: R, Python, and MATLAB [54]. The platform also offers an innovative feature: analytical scripts can be translated into web services, significantly enhancing their long-term reproducibility. Once published, these services can be accessed either through a graphical user interface, or via RESTful API calls for machine-to-machine interactions.

The interaction between DataLabs and the Data Portal is bidirectional: users can import datasets into their research projects, and they can also upload both local files used as input within their scripts and the output generated by the resulting services or scripts. All these actions are automatically reflected in the Metadata Catalogue, helping researchers build complete, well-documented, and highly reproducible analytics, while ensuring full provenance and traceability across the entire data lifecycle.

Scripts and services created within DataLabs can be utilised as building blocks to develop new workflows and VREs, supporting dynamic, repeatable, and scalable scientific investigations [55].

2.5 Reuse

To ensure widespread and effective adoption of the LifeWatch Italy infrastructure, key platforms have been integrated with two essential support services: the e-Training Platform [56] and the Help Desk [57].

e-Training Platform. The e-Training Platform provides a dedicated online space for capacity building. It hosts a wide range of guidelines, tutorials, and educational content aimed at facilitating the effective use of the infrastructure and its various components.

Helpdesk. The Help Desk offers user support via a ticketing system, enabling users to receive technical assistance and guidance on using the infrastructure's platforms and services. It is designed to streamline troubleshooting and improve user experience across the digital ecosystem.

3 Future developments and considerations

The LifeWatch Italy infrastructure, while already fully operational, is also in continuous development (see Fig. 1). The vision is to create a unified and interconnected ecosystem of services and platforms, where all digital research products, i.e. datasets, metadata, analytical scripts, web services, semantic artefacts, etc. are all

accessible through a single infrastructure. To anticipate this interconnection, the platforms of the Infrastructure is already accessible through a Single Sign-On system, allowing users to move across platforms and services using a unique account.

One of the primary goals for future development is the consolidation of platform interconnection. While platforms such as the Data Portal, Metadata Catalogue, DataLabs, Bioacoustic Platform, and Citizen Science Platform already serve distinct purposes, their full integration is still in progress (see dotted lines in Fig. 1). The ambition is to ensure that research products generated or submitted within one platform are automatically referenced or shared to other platforms or services wherever meaningful connections are established. For instance, when a user uploads an audio file to the Bioacoustic Platform or data is collected through citizen science initiatives, (meta)data should become discoverable through the Data Portal and Metadata Catalogue, ultimately linked to taxonomic references and eventually reused for downstream analyses.

Achieving such interoperability requires standardised data and metadata flows, persistent identifiers, and shared vocabularies across all services. Furthermore, interfaces and APIs are under continuous development to support real-time synchronisation and automated cross-referencing among services.

There are also strategic considerations related to long-term sustainability and user engagement. As the infrastructure evolves, maintaining coherence and usability will require a structured governance, continuous feedback from users, coordination with the broader LifeWatch ERIC infrastructure, and alignment with emerging FAIR practices and standards. It is also important to acknowledge that building and maintaining such an infrastructure is not solely a technical challenge. Sustained financial investment is crucial to ensure the long-term viability of the platforms, their underlying services, and the storage and computational resources required to support them. Equally critical is the availability of skilled personnel. Technical (ICT specialists, data stewards) and scientific (data scientists, informaticians) staff who can manage editorial workflows, provide user support, develop new features, and ensure alignment with international standards and community needs. The value of the infrastructure lies not only in its technology but in the human capacity to curate, validate, and promote the effective use of available research products.

In the coming years, efforts will be directed toward closing remaining technical and operational gaps, fostering full platform integration, and enhancing the overall user experience. The ultimate aim is to offer a robust, open, and FAIR-compliant hub for biodiversity and ecosystem data in Italy, capable of supporting cutting-edge research, policy, and conservation efforts.

Acknowledgments. This work has been supported by the PON-IR “LifeWatchPLUS” (CIR01_00028; PIR01_00028) and Next Generation EU Mission 4 “Education and Research” – Component 2: “From research to business” – Investment 3.1: “Fund for the realisation of an integrated system of research and innovation infrastructures” – Project IR0000032 – ITINERIS – Italian Integrated Environmental Research Infrastructures System – CUP B53C22002150006.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

References

- Pereira, H. M., Martins, I. S., Rosa, I. M. D., Kim, H., Leadley, P., Popp, A., et al.: Global trends and scenarios for terrestrial biodiversity and ecosystem services from 1900 to 2050. *Science* **384**, 458-465 (2024). <https://science.org/doi/10.1126/science.adn3441>
- Navarro, L. M., Fernandez, N., Guerra, C., Guralnick, R., Kissling, W. D., Londoño, M. C., et al.: Monitoring biodiversity change through effective global coordination. *Current opinion in environmental sustainability*, **29**, 158-169 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2018.02.005>
- Kühl, H. S., Bowler, D. E., Bösch, L., Bruelheide, H., Dauber, J., Eichenberg, D., et al.: Effective biodiversity monitoring needs a culture of integration. *One Earth*, **3**(4), 462-474 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2020.09.010>
- Chen, X., Jagerhorn, M.: Implementing FAIR Workflows along the research lifecycle. *Procedia Computer Science*, **211**, 83-92 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2022.10.179>
- Güntsch A., Overmann J., Ebert B., Bonn A., Le Bras Y., Engel T., et al.: National biodiversity data infrastructures: ten essential functions for science, policy, and practice. *BioScience*, **75**(2), 139–151 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biae109>
- Global Biodiversity Information Facility, GBIF Homepage, <https://www.gbif.org/>, last accessed 2025/06/11
- Sweet, F. S. T., Apfelbeck, B., Hanusch, M., Garland Monteagudo, C., Weisser, W. W.: Data from public and governmental databases show that a large proportion of the regional animal species pool occur in cities in Germany. *Journal of Urban Ecology*, **8**(1), juac002 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1093/jue/juac002>
- Reichman, O. J., Jones, M. B., Schildhauer, M. P.: Challenges and opportunities of open data in ecology. *Science*, **331**(6018), 703-705 (2011). <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/7627s45z>
- McCleery, R., Guralnick, R., Beatty, M., Belitz, M., Campbell, C. J., Idec, J., et al.: Uniting experiments and big data to advance ecology and conservation. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, **38**(10), 970-979 (2023). <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0169534723001337>
- Di Muri, C., Pulieri, M., Raho, D., Muresan, A. N., Tarallo, a., Titocci, J. et al.: Assessing semantic interoperability in environmental sciences: variety of approaches and semantic artefacts. *Scientific Data* **11**, 1055 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-024-03669-3>
- Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., et al.: The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data* **3**, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- D. Peterson, J., Kasperowski, D., van der Wal, R.: Bringing Together Species Observations: A Case Story of Sweden’s Biodiversity Informatics Infrastructures. *Minerva* **61**, 265–289 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11024-023-09491-2>
- Schulman, L., Lahti, K., Piirainen, E., Heikkinen, M., Raitio, O., Juslén, A.: The Finnish Biodiversity Information Facility as a best-practice model for biodiversity data infrastructures. *Scientific Data* **8**, 137 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-021-00919-6>
- LifeWatch Italy Homepage, <https://www.lifewatchitaly.eu/>, last accessed 2025/06/11
- LifeWatch ERIC Homepage, <https://www.lifewatch.eu/>, last accessed 2025/06/11
- Hognogi, G. G., Meltzer, M., Alexandrescu, F., Stefanescu, L.: The role of citizen science mobile apps in facilitating a contemporary digital agora. *Humanities and Social Science Communications* **10**, 863 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-02358-7>
- LifeWatch Italy Citizen Science Homepage, <https://citizenscience.lifewatchitaly.eu/>, last accessed 2025/06/11

18. BioAcoustic Homepage, <https://bioacoustics.lifewatchitaly.eu/>, last accessed 2025/06/11
19. Cheung, S. Y., Leung, Y. F., Larson, L. R.: Citizen science as a tool for enhancing recreation research in protected areas: Applications and opportunities. *Journal of environmental management*, **305**, 114353 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.114353>
20. Stephenson, P. J.: Technological advances in biodiversity monitoring: Applicability, opportunities and challenges. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, **45**, 36-41 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2020.08.005>
21. Znidarsic, E., Towsey, M., Roy, W. K., Darling, S. E., Truskinger, A., Roe, P., et al.: Using visualization and machine learning methods to monitor low detectability species - The least bittern as a case study. *Ecological Informatics*, **55**, 101014 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2019.101014>
22. Sinaci, A. A., Núñez-Benjumea, F. J., Gencturk, M., Jauer, M. L., Deserno, T., Chronaki, C., et al.: From Raw Data to FAIR Data: The FAIRification Workflow for Health Research. *Methods of Information in Medicine* **59**(S01), e21-e32 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0040-1713684>
23. LifeWatch Italy DataPortal. <https://data.lifewatchitaly.eu/>, last accessed 2025/06/11
24. Jones, M. B., O'Brien, M., Mecum, B., Boettiger, C., Schildhauer, M., Maier, M., et al.: Ecological Metadata Language version 2.2.0. KNB Data Repository. <https://doi.org/10.5063/F11834T2>
25. Darwin Core Maintenance Group. List of Darwin Core terms. Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) (2021). <http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/doc/list/>, last accessed 2025/06/11
26. Catalogue of Life Homepage, <https://www.catalogueoflife.org/>, last accessed 2025/06/11
27. World Register of Marine Species Homepage, <https://www.marinespecies.org/>, last accessed 2025/06/11
28. World flora Online, <https://www.worldfloraonline.org/>, last accessed 2025/06/11
29. EcoPortal, <https://ecoportal.lifewatch.eu/>, last accessed 2025/06/11
30. Chong, S.S., Schildhauer, M., O'Brien, M., Mecum, B. and Jones, M.B.: Enhancing the FAIRness of Arctic Research Data Through Semantic Annotation. *Data Science Journal*, **23**(1), 2 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2024-002>
31. Kennedy, J. B., Kukla, R., Paterson, T.: Scientific names are ambiguous as identifiers for biological taxa: their context and definition are required for accurate data integration. In: Ludäscher, B., Raschid, L. (eds) *Data Integration in the Life Sciences. DILS 2005. Lecture Notes in Computer Science* (2005), vol 3615. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/11530084_8
32. Grenié, M., Berti, E., Carvajal-Quintero, J., Dädlow, G. M., Sagouis, A., Winter, M.: Harmonizing taxon names in biodiversity data: A review of tools, databases and best practices. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, **14**, 12–25 (2005). <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13802>
33. Costello, M. J.: Taxonomy as the key to life. *Megataxa*, **001**(2), 105-113 (2020). <http://dx.doi.org/10.11646/megataxa.1.2.1>
34. Garnett, S. T., Christidis, L., Conix, S., Costello, M. J., Zachos, F. E., Bánki, O. S., et al.: Principles for creating a single authoritative list of the world's species. *PLOS Biology* **18**(7), e3000736 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000736>
35. König, C., Weigelt, P., Schrader, J., Taylor, A., Kattge, J., KrefT, H.: Biodiversity data integration - the significance of data resolution and domain. *PLOS Biology* **17**(3), e3000183 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000183>
36. Bologna, M. A., Zapparoli, M., Olivero, M., Minelli, A., Bonato, L., Cianferoni, F.: Italian Fauna Checklist. LifeWatch Italy Data Portal, (2021). <https://data.lifewatchitaly.eu/handle/123456789/129792>.

37. Portal to the Flora of Italy, <http://dryades.units.it/floritaly>, last accessed 2025/06/11
38. Martellos, S., Conti, M., Nimis, P.L.: Aggregation of Italian Lichen Data in ITALIC 7.0. *Journal of Fungi*, **9**(5), 556 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof9050556>
39. LifeWatch Italy Italian Taxonomic Backbone <https://taxonomicbackbone.lifewatchitaly.eu/>, last accessed 2025/06/11
40. Todman, L. C., Bush, A., Hood, A. S.: ‘Small Data’ for big insights in ecology. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, **38**(7), 615-622 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2023.01.015>
41. Falster, D., Gallagher, R., Wenk, E. H., Wright, I. J., Indriarto, D., Andrew, S. C., et al.: AusTraits, a curated plant trait database for the Australian flora. *Scientific Data*, **8**, 254 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-021-01006-6>
42. Le Guillarme, N., Hedde, M., Potapov, A. M., Martínez-Muñoz, C. A., Berg, M. P., Briones, M. J., et al.: The soil food web ontology: aligning trophic groups, processes, resources, and dietary traits to support food-web research. *Ecological Informatics*, **78**, 102360 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2023.102360>
43. Semantic Sensor Network Ontology, SOSA, <https://www.w3.org/TR/2017/REC-vocab-ssn-20171019/>, last accessed 2025/06/11
44. PROV-O: The PROV Ontology, <http://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>, last accessed 2025/06/11
45. Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) - Version 3, <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>, last accessed 2025/06/11
46. LifeWatch Italy Semantic Platform, <https://semantics.lifewatchitaly.eu/>, last accessed 2025/06/11
47. LifeWatch Italy Metadata Catalogue, <https://metadatatatalogue.lifewatchitaly.eu/>, last accessed 2025/06/11
48. F-UJI Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool, <https://www.f-uji.net>, last accessed 2025/06/11
49. Huber, R.: FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics (0.8). Zenodo (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15045911>
50. Farley, S. S., Dawson, A., Goring, S. J., Williams, J. W.: Situating Ecology as a Big-Data Science: Current Advances, Challenges, and Solutions. *BioScience*, **68**(8), 563–576 (2018). <https://www.jstor.org/stable/90023897>
51. Tanhua, T., Pouliquen, S., Hausman, J., O’Brien, K., Bricher, P., De Bruin, T., et al.: Ocean FAIR data services. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, **6**, 440 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00440>
52. LifeWatch Italy DataLabs. <https://datalabs.lifewatchitaly.eu/>, last accessed 2025/06/11
53. Kluyver, T., Ragan-Kelley, B., Pérez, F., Granger, B., Bussonnier, M., Frederic, J., et al.: Jupyter Notebooks – a publishing format for reproducible computational workflows. In: F. Loizides & B. Schmidt (Eds.), *Positioning and Power in Academic Publishing: Players, Agents and Agendas* (pp. 87–90). IOS Press (2016).
54. Kambouris, S., Wilkinson, D. P., Smith, E.T., Fidler, F.: Computationally reproducing results from meta-analyses in ecology and evolutionary biology using shared code and data. *PLOS One*, **19**(3), e0300333 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0300333>
55. Zhao, Z., Koulouzis, S., Bianchi, R., Farshidi, S., Shi, Z., Xin, R. et al.: Notebook-as-a-VRE (NaaVRE): From private notebooks to a collaborative cloud virtual research environment. *Software: Practice and Experience*, **52**(9), 1947–1966 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1002/spe.3098>
56. LifeWatch Italy Training Platform. <https://training.lifewatchitaly.eu/>, last accessed 2025/06/11
57. LifeWatch Italy Help-Desk, <https://helpdesk.lifewatchitaly.eu/>, last accessed 2025/06/11